

Performance appraisal and job satisfaction for workers without and with disabilities by gender

Abstract

This study analyses the effects of performance appraisal on the levels of job satisfaction reported by workers without and with disabilities (aged 16-64) by gender. Particularly, we are interested in investigating the impact of monetary rewards such as pay, bonuses, future raises and potential promotion on job satisfaction by disability status and checking differences by gender. Our data come from the German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP) for the years 2004, 2008, 2011 and 2016. We estimate job satisfaction equations running a fixed effect "Probit Adapted OLS" model. We find that males with disabilities are less likely to be satisfied with their jobs when they are subject to performance appraisal with monetary effects (appraisals with both short and long-term rewards explain this result), whereas the opposite result is found for females with disabilities (in the case of receiving long-term rewards). We estimate the association of these performance appraisal schemes with recognition from superiors, and with their efforts, personal advances and pay, and we find a coherent pattern with previous results.

1 Introduction

The objective of this article consists of analysing how performance related pay affects job satisfaction for people without and with disabilities, by gender. The literature on the reactions of workers with disabilities to reward systems is rather scarce (Witte et al, 1998; Shantz et al, 2018), and shows that these workers systematically report lower levels of pay satisfaction than those without disabilities. The most important explanation for this relationship is a lack of trust in management. However, these results only refer to pay satisfaction and not to job satisfaction in general, and do not consider differences by gender, when there is a known difference in job satisfaction by gender for the whole population (Clark, 1997) and, specifically, among people with disabilities (Pagan and Malo, 2009). Although, there is a negative influence of disability on job satisfaction, women with disabilities report a positive differential respect to men with disabilities even after controlling by the confounding effects of other variables (Pagan and Malo, 2009).

Therefore, we can expect differences in the impact of performance related pay for women with disabilities respect to their male counterparts.

Worker motivation is a complex process depending on many factors (Franco et al., 2002), as psychological, organizational, human resources management, social and, also, financial considerations. In fact, there are plenty of results showing that performance related pay can be implemented through different incentive schemes work (Lucifora, 2015). They have positive impacts on different outcomes as productivity (Lazear, 2000; Gielen et al., 2010; Lucifora and Origo, 2015), but also on job satisfaction of the average worker (Heywood and Wei, 2006). In general, employees' earnings are highest where performance related pay are present at the workplace (McNabb and Whitfield, 2007). However, not all incentives are equally important in the same way and they can have adverse effects for some groups of workers. The impact of individual incentives is larger than for the rest of group incentives (e.g. teamwork incentives, profit-sharing, and share ownership), although the total effect is composed by a direct effect -i.e. incentive increases productivity- and an indirect effect through sorting -i.e. performance related pay attracts more productive workers- (Lucifora, 2015). This last point is worrying when focusing on some disadvantaged groups – e.g. those workers who are disabled.

The weaker position of disadvantaged workers may backfire incentives schemes. Performance related pay requires a monitoring process -usually including a formal system- based on the judgements, opinions and evaluations of managers, supervisors, peers, and, sometimes, even worker themselves (Jackson and Schuler 2003). However, performance appraisal systems might lead to unfair treatment, inequalities in procedures, a tendency toward centrality and biased evaluations -e.g. because of a supervisor's misperceptions and lack of objectivity in evaluating efforts and performance not taking into account workers' diversity. These problems lead to real injustice and discriminatory

presumptions against some disadvantageous groups -e.g. immigrants, females, the elderly, or those workers who are disabled- in the labour market (Thursthon and McNall, 2009; Grund and Przemec, 2012; Rowland and Hall, 2012). In addition, previous literature also shows consistent differences by gender, suggesting that the link between the payment method and wage is not universal; in particular, women do not report additional satisfaction from profit sharing schemes (Heywood and Wei, 2006). In the case of workers with disabilities, they may feel that a performance related pay is not an equal treatment policy if it is not explicitly designed to take into account their special needs or jointly implemented with an effective management policy (Shantz et al., 2018). In addition, individual incentives increase the variance of workers' earnings (Prendergast, 1999; Lazear, 2000), which will be not well received by risk averse workers such as workers with disabilities. In any incentives' scheme, there is a trade-off between efficiency and insurance, and risk averse workers -i.e. people with disabilities- might prefer insurance to efficiency, decreasing earnings variance. Being under a performance related pay scheme may expose workers to (subjective) excessive levels of risk, which would be counterproductive for the firm and decrease workers' job satisfaction (Prendergast, 1999). Finally, the implementation of a performance related pay may increase earnings but also psychological stress, which may be harmful for workers' health in the long term (Lucifora, 2015). In this vein, Pagan (2014) estimates the trade-offs between different non-pecuniary job's characteristics and earnings to keep job satisfaction constant. He finds that workers with disabilities are willing to sacrifice more earnings than workers without disabilities in order to avoid a stressing workplace.

Considering the technical characteristics of our empirical analysis, we use a longitudinal rich database, the German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP) for the years 2004, 2008, 2011, and 2016. We use detailed information on individual -as disability status,

gender, etc.- and job characteristics, especially monetary rewards -i.e. wages, bonuses, future raises, and potential promotions. We estimate fixed effects models introduced by van Praag et al. (2003) called the “Probit Adapted OLS (POLS)”.

Finally, our results can help increase the public, social and economic debate on the usually less-favourable working conditions of workers with disabilities, and contribute to ensuring a fairer, and more transparent, objective and equalitarian treatment for them as they are monitored and evaluated under a formal performance appraisal system.

2 Review of the literature and main hypotheses

There is an extensive body of research on performance appraisal (e.g. Milkovich and Wigdor 1991; Keeping and Levy 2000; Levy and Williams 2004; Brown and Heywood, 2005; Grund and Sliwka, 2009; Cornelissen et al., 2011; Jirjahn and Poutsma, 2013; and Heywood et al., 2017). Nevertheless, the interest of this literature has been focused on productivity (Prendergast, 1999; Lucifora, 2015), and the relationship between performance appraisal and workers’ job satisfaction has been much less analysed.

In this vein, Judge et al. (2001) present a qualitative and quantitative revision of the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance, finding a highly significant correlation between these two variables (around 0.3 points), and consistent with the results of other researchers as Whitman et al. (2010). According to Pettijohn et al. (2001) and Agyare et al. (2013), job satisfaction increases when performance appraisal is based on clear and well-defined criteria, meeting with workers’ approval, being perceived as fair, linking appraisals to promotion, and establishing clarity of roles and providing feedback about their performance. Furthermore, Deepa et al. (2014) point out the importance of work engagement in terms of job satisfaction and its effects on performance appraisals.

In our case, the work of Kampkötter (2017) is particularly relevant because it also uses longitudinal data from the SOEP (compared to most previous studies that have used cross-sectional data), and is the first to distinguish between monetary and non-monetary outcomes of performance appraisal, and their effect on workers' job satisfaction. He finds that receiving formal performance appraisal has a significant and positive impact on job satisfaction, but only when appraisals have monetary consequences. He also includes in his regressions information on locus control and the "Big Five" personality traits (i.e. extraversion, conscientiousness, neuroticism, openness to experience, and agreeableness), although the coefficients on the corresponding interaction terms with performance appraisal are not significant at the 5% level. Finally, he concludes that the utilization of performance appraisals without monetary effects can be harmful for those workers (e.g. open-minded and self-determined individuals) whose expectations are not fulfilled in the workplace.

Focusing on workers with disabilities, there are two key papers on the effects of performance related pay on job satisfaction, Witte et al. (1998) and Shantz et al. (2018). The first one consists of a comparison of 55 self-identified college graduates with learning disabilities and 55 control matched graduates by gender, major, degree, and graduation year, without this type of disabilities. All of them graduated from the same US Midwestern University. The analysis shows that graduates with learning disabilities perceived that they received less pay and promotion opportunities, and reported lower levels of job satisfaction, respect to the control group. Nevertheless, the authors did not find a significant difference in wages between both groups. In any case, the graduates with learning disabilities believed they were not adequately compensated for their work, and this dissatisfaction at work was reached relatively early in their working careers. Witte et al. (1998) consider that their results present some limitations for generalization,

but they open the door to take seriously that workers with disabilities probably feel that there is not an equal treatment rule for them about pay.

Shantz et al. (2018) provide a much wider study, using a representative survey of the United Kingdom (the 2011 British Workplace Employee Relations Survey) and a rich set of questions about the management practices in the organizations were the interviewees work. They obtain strong evidence that disability decreases pay satisfaction and when there is an incentive scheme of performance related pay, then their negative pay satisfaction differential is larger. However, when disability-related management policies and practices are both present, the gap in pay satisfaction is narrower. It is important to remark that this result is obtained not for having an explicit management policy towards workers with disabilities, but when individuals report that these policies are effectively implemented. The authors connect these results with the existence of trust in management and taking into account the peculiarities of disabilities in the performance evaluation of incentives' schemes.

Considering together all these results, a potential explanation emerges: evaluation systems created for an average worker may be unfair for workers with disabilities if adaptation or special needs are not considered by supervisors, evaluation indicators, etc. It is worthwhile mentioning the works of Schur et al. (2009) and Pagan (2014), which analyse the working conditions of employees with disabilities in terms of pay, promotion, task diversity, capacity to decide, and conflicts and difficulty with supervisors, among others. According to Schur et al. (2009), who use data of 30,000 employee surveys from 14 companies in the USA, workers with disabilities receive lower wages, have less job security, lower levels of participation in job and department decisions, are more closely supervised, and are less likely to receive company-sponsored training and potential promotions as compared to their non-disabled counterparts. They also mention that the

existence of a “*justice climate*” based on the principles of distributive, procedural, and interpersonal justice in the organization (Liao, 2007; Rupp et al., 2007) are very important for workers with disabilities because “distributive justice concerns outcomes such as pay and the provision of workplace accommodations, procedural justice concerns policies and procedures such as how requests for accommodations are handled, and interpersonal justice concerns the extent to which organizational members are treated with respect, dignity, and sensitivity (pp. 384)”. The presence of discrimination and negative stereotypes and attitudes toward workers with disabilities (Baldwin and Johnson, 2006) may have a strong impact on their employment opportunities and experiences, and thus their performance reviews and levels of job satisfaction (Schur et al., 2009). As for the latter, Pagan (2014), using data from the SOEP for five waves (1985, 1987, 1989, 1995 and 2001), explores the importance of non-pecuniary characteristics in terms of job satisfaction for workers with disabilities, and finds that “hard manual work, the existence of unhealthy environments, and the levels of conflicts with supervisors are more important than pay in determining overall job satisfaction (pp. 245)”. He mentions, that the presence of “*intrinsic*” rewards such as, for example, friendly supervisors, capacity to learn new things on the job, and safety and healthy workplaces can contribute to increasing their levels of motivation because the effects tend to be longer, as Herzberg (1968) pointed out. Pagan (2014) also finds that being monitored in the workplace has a significant negative effect on job satisfaction for all workers (disabled or not).

According to Shantz et al. (2018), the Equity Theory proposed by Adams (1963) provides a theoretical framework to understand the negative effect of incentives schemes on job satisfaction of workers with disabilities. Following Adams (1963), employers (and supervisors) must find a fair and adequate balance between the inputs that a worker gives (i.e. effort, skills, loyalty, ability, hard work, performance, commitment and trust) and the

outcomes received (i.e. pay, recognition, reputation, responsibility, sense of growth, and job security). The “norm of equity” states that individuals are equally sensitive to equity, i.e., the general preference is that outcome/input ratio be equal to that of the comparison group (Huseman et al., 1987). Inequality appears when the worker (e.g. with disabilities) compares his/her outcome/income ratio to that obtained by a similar worker (e.g. without disabilities), and this leads to a sense of unfairness and dissatisfaction (Adams, 1963).

Performance systems with monetary effects based on prejudices and pre-existing negative stereotypes against people with disabilities may provoke situations of injustice and dissatisfaction with respect to the outcome/input ratio received by these workers and that of their non-disabled counterparts. Furthermore, performance appraisal may be based on unfair procedures (e.g. timeliness, setting goals and feedback) and inflexible specifications (e.g. restraining the necessity of workplace accommodations or the use of flexible schedules for workers with disabilities), which contribute to keeping or even increasing the levels of injustice and dissatisfaction among workers with disabilities. According to Kampkötter (2017), some workers (e.g. with disabilities) may suffer restrictions in how they organise their work and perform their tasks and obligations, which contribute to reducing significantly their levels of job satisfaction. Focusing on workers with disabilities, Uppal (2005) finds that these groups of workers are very concerned with how much they earn as compared to the earnings of other individuals with similar characteristics. If we apply this idea to our case of performance appraisal and follow the foundations of the Equity Theory, we may argue that, for example, the presence of rigid rules and inflexible procedures, excessive bureaucracy, un-trained supervisors, tangible and intangible barriers, and inadequate information systems may lead to a sense of unfair treatment for all workers.

Should we expect differences in the effect of performance related pay on job satisfaction of workers with disabilities by gender? There is no any previous research focusing on these potential differences. However, some previous results may shed some light. Following Malo and Pagan (2012), females with disabilities usually have lower expectations about their jobs compared to males with disabilities, and this fact may lead to a reduction of the effects of performance appraisal on job satisfaction. This is in line with a more general result obtained by Clark (1997), who found consistently higher levels of satisfaction for female workers with respect to males (*ceteris paribus*), but also in line with the positive differential of job satisfaction of workers with disabilities respect to those without them (*ceteris paribus*).

To sum up, in accordance with the aforementioned reasons, we state the following two hypotheses:

- *Hypothesis 1: Performance appraisal with monetary effects decreases job satisfaction among male workers with disabilities.*
- *Hypothesis 2: Performance appraisal with monetary effects does not decrease job satisfaction among female workers with disabilities.*

In the case of Hypothesis 1, the causal channel would be the feeling of unfair treatment, while in the case of Hypothesis 2 the causal channel would be the lower expectations about their jobs. The subsequent empirical analysis will check both hypotheses, and how the different causal channels may operate.

3 Data, measures and method

Sample

For the present study, we have taken data from the German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP), a large-scale longitudinal dataset (first started in 1984) that covers a wide set of

areas and topics, including information on individual and household characteristics, employment status, working conditions, earnings, health, satisfaction measures, and hours of work, among others (for more information, see, for example, Wagner et al., 2007). This dataset is periodically refreshed with new samples and around 30,000 individuals in nearly 11,000 private households are interviewed on an annual basis. Although the SOEP provides information for the period 1984-2016 (version 33), we only use 2004, 2008, 2011 and 2016 because it is only for those years wherein our key variable “*performance appraisal*” is available. We restrict our sample to workers aged 16-64. Similar to Kampkötter (2017) and Heywood *et al.* (2017), we excluded from this sample self-employed, freelance professionals, apprentices, trainees, and marginal workers (those with monthly earnings below 450 euros) because they are less likely to receive performance appraisals. As a result, and after excluding observations with missing values, our final samples used in the estimation process consist of 15,679 (15,092 non-disabled +587 disabled) and 14,036 (13,494 non-disabled+542 disabled) person-year observations for males and females, respectively (which are 9,140 (8,681 non-disabled+459 disabled) and 8,533 individuals (8,079 non-disabled+454 disabled), each observed on average for 1.7 and 1.6 different years, respectively).

Measures

Data on performance appraisals are obtained from the following SOEP question: “*Is your own performance regularly assessed by a superior as part of an agreed procedure? (Yes/No)*”. For those workers who answer “Yes”, the follow-up question is: “*Does this performance assessment influence...: a) your monthly gross salary; b) a yearly bonus; c) future salary increases; and d) potential promotion? (Yes/No)*”. This question permits multiple responses. Using the responses to these two questions and similar to Kampkötter (2017), we create a variable called “*performance appraisal*” that takes 3 possible values:

1= if the individual's performance is not assessed (i.e. those individuals responding "No" to the first question); 2= if the individual's performance is assessed but without monetary effects (i.e. those individuals responding "Yes" to the first question and "No" to all possible options included in the second question); and 3= if the individual's performance is assessed and has monetary effects (those individual responding "Yes" to the first question, and "Yes" to any of the four options mentioned above). Heywood *et al.* (2017) also propose the possibility to distinguish between short and long term monetary effects. To do this, they identify short-term monetary effects as those on the monthly gross salary or annual bonus, whereas long-term monetary effects are those on future salary increases or potential promotion. We also use this classification proposed by Heywood *et al.* (2017) in order to check the robustness of our estimation results later on.

As for job satisfaction, we have used the following question: "*How satisfied are you with your job?*". The possible answers range from 0 (completely dissatisfied) to 10 (completely satisfied). Therefore, we have used self-reported data on individuals' job satisfaction¹. Ferrer-i-Carbonell and Frijters (2004) point out that psychologists and sociologists (e.g. Schwartz 1995; Ng 1997) usually interpret happiness scores as cardinal and comparable across respondents, and run OLS regressions on happiness and changes in happiness. On contrary, economists (e.g. van Praag 1991; Ferrer-i-Carbonell and Frijters 2004) usually assume only ordinality of the answers because individuals can recognise and predict the satisfaction levels of others and translate verbal labels, such as "*very good*" and "*very bad*", into roughly the same numerical values, and have mainly

¹ According to the existing literature (e.g. Kristensen and Johansson, 2008; Bonsang and van Soest, 2012; Knott et al., 2017), one of the problem of using self-evaluations of overall happiness or job satisfaction is that individuals from different countries, cultures or socio-economic backgrounds may perceive these questions on satisfaction in different ways, and may use different response scales (i.e. differential item functioning, DIF). To avoid this problem, the use of anchoring vignettes (wherein individuals evaluate, on the same scale, how good or bad are different hypothetical job or life situations) contributes to identifying these interpersonal differentials in response scales (King et al., 2004). In our case, unfortunately we cannot use this technique with the information on performance appraisal included in the SOEP.

used ordered latent response models. According to Ferrer-i-Carbonell and Frijters (2004), two psychological findings support this assumption. First, they point out that “individuals are somewhat able to recognise and predict the satisfaction level of others, and there exists a common human language of satisfaction and that satisfaction is roughly observable and comparable among individuals. Second, individuals in the same language community have a common understanding of how to translate internal feelings into a number scale, simply in order for individuals to be able to communicate with each other (pp. 644)”. However, Ferrer-i-Carbonell and Frijters (2004) conclude that “assuming ordinality or cardinality of happiness scores makes little difference, whilst allowing for fixed-effects does change results substantially (pp. 641)”.

As for our disability measure, we follow the works of Burkhauser and Daly (1998), Jenkins and Riggs (2004), Burkhauser et al. (2006) and Pagan (2010), and based on whether the individual reports a work-limiting health condition. Despite the fact that the use of this type of disability measures is controversial (Stapleton and Burkhauser, 2003), some studies have found that self-reported measures of work limitation are highly correlated with both objective assessments of health and clinical measures of disability. In the SOEP, the question on work-limitation has been changed over time, and it has not been asked in all its waves (from 1988 to 1991 and in 1993 and 1994, or at all from 2002 onwards). To overcome this limitation, Burkhauser and Schroeder (2007), using the existence of this work-limitation question as a benchmark when available, have created a work limitation-based measure of disability for all SOEP years that is comparable to that work-limitation question included in the Current Population Survey (CPS) of the United States. To do this, they use two questions (included each year) on satisfaction with health (which is a completely subjective measure that is likely to be highly correlated with a self-perceived work limitation) and the degree of officially registered disability (because

it directly captures part of the population with disabilities). Burkhauser and Schroeder (2007) offer two possible ways to construct a consistent measure of disability in all years. The first is to predict what they regard as the true disability status with an estimation of limited dependent variables, using the health satisfaction and the degree of disability as explanatory variables (logit indicator). The second is to find combinations of different levels of health satisfaction and degrees of disability, and see how these match with the true measure of limitation (combination indicator). They find that both measures consistently place more than 90 percent of the sample in the correct category and follow the trends of the true measure well. However, the combination measure is easier to compute and, more importantly, is not subject to the choice of an estimation procedure or the imprecision of prediction. After running diverse regressions and models, they conclude that a person is considered disabled if he or she has a health satisfaction level of at most 2 or a degree of disability of at least 53%². Namely, those individuals who fulfil at least one of these two conditions are considered disabled.

Pagan (2010, 2011) demonstrates that the variable “*satisfaction with health*” used in this definition of disability is not problematic in the analysis of the effects of disability on “*satisfaction with job*”. According to Pagan (2010, 2011) the variables disability and health do not share exactly the same information. Intuitively, we can take the example of blindness. When it is generated by a chronic illness (such as diabetes) it is probably linked to poor health status, but when blindness is related to a congenital vision problem, this disability and the health status of the individual will probably be orthogonal³.

² They also use the created measures of disability from the SOEP to estimate the prevalence of disability for working-age men (aged 21-58) in the western states of Germany between 1984 and 2002. They also compare the employment of the working-age men with disabilities relative to their counterparts without disabilities in Germany and in the United States. They demonstrate the consistency and validity of the combination measure to investigate the impact of different disability policies and policy changes in Germany alone or in comparison with the United States.

³ Similar to Pagan (2010), we have analysed the relationship between disability and health satisfaction in order to test that both variables do not correlate perfectly. For this purpose, we have calculated the relationship between disability and health satisfaction for our samples of reference. We found that 27.1%

Furthermore, according to Burkhauser and Schroeder (2007), if we used only the degree of disability measure to identify the disabled population, we would miss individuals with a work limitation who were in the process of becoming registered and who had short-term limitations or had decided it was not worth registering. Despite these limitations, we have also used the official registration measure to identify workers with disabilities in order to check for the robustness and sensitivity of our econometric results.

To shed further light on the relationship between “performance appraisal” and “disability”, we can also find in the SOEP questionnaire for the year 2011 a set of questions concerning the level of recognition of individuals at work: “a) *I receive the recognition I deserve from my superiors; b) When I consider all my accomplishments and efforts, the recognition I have received seems fitting; c) When I consider all my accomplishments and efforts, my chances of personal advancement seem fitting; and d) When I consider all my accomplishments and efforts, my pay seems appropriate*”. The possible answers are: Yes/No, and if the individual responds “No”, the follow-up question is: “*And how much does it burden you? (Not at all, somewhat, heavily, and very heavily)*”. From these responses, we have created four variables (i.e. recognition from superiors, with effort, with advances, and with pay) which have been coded from 1 (No recognition, burdening very heavily) to 5 (Yes recognition).

Method

of people with disabilities (31.02 and 23.46% for males and females, respectively) have a health satisfaction score equal to or over 5 points. This result is even higher than that obtained by Pagan (2010). Similar to Pagan (2010), this percentage for people without disabilities goes up to 89.89% (90.27 and 89.13% for males and females, respectively). These results are also in line with other psychological studies that conclude that the domain of disability extends far beyond health related concerns to encompass the person’s well-being, definition of self and social position (Grimby et al., 1988). Therefore, in studying disability, it is critical not to restrict the notion of job satisfaction to health related issues.

Similar to other empirical works on job satisfaction, we follow the work of Clark and Oswald (1996) to estimate the determinants of job satisfaction, and based on the following individual's utility from working:

$$U = u(y, h, i, w) \quad [1]$$

where y is income, h is hours of work and i and w are a set of variables measuring the individual and job characteristics, respectively. Ordered responses models (e.g. ordered probit (OP) and ordered logit (OL) models) have been traditionally used in the previous literature on job satisfaction. However, van Praag and Ferrer-i- Carbonell (2006) point out that “when we try to apply ordered response models on more general models than the simple OLS-equation we easily run into difficulties (pp. 5)”⁴. In our case, we have estimated a “Probit Adapted OLS (POLs)” model proposed by van Praag et al. (2003), and based on the transformation of the data that allows discrete choice variables as if they are distributed along the whole real line. To use POLs, first our dependent variable (i.e. job satisfaction (JS) that is categorical, naturally ordered and with c categories (in our case, c is from 0 (completely dissatisfied) to 10 (completely dissatisfied)) must be transformed in their conditional expectations according to the properties of the normal distribution (Maddala, 1983). To do this, we use the method proposed by Terza (1987), and assign a JS value to each c category by setting:

$$JS_c^T = E(JS \mid \mu_{c-1} < JS \leq \mu_c) = (n(\mu_{c-1}) - n(\mu_c)) / (N(\mu_c) - N(\mu_{c-1})) \quad c = 0, \dots, 10 \quad [2]$$

⁴ For instance, “when we like to apply these models in panel analysis where we want to take into account the panel structure either by assuming that the error terms between different observations of the same individual are correlated (individual random effects) or by introducing individual fixed effects many computational problems appear, when the one dimensional integrals have to be replaced by multi-dimensional integrals, where integration problems tend to become overwhelming (van Praag and Ferrer-i- Carbonell (2006, pp. 5))”.

where JS^T_c is the transformed job satisfaction variable for each c category, N is the normal distribution function, n is the normal density function, and μ_c are the values for which it holds that $N(\mu_c) - N(\mu_{c-1})$ is the fraction of respondents belonging to category c for JS. In our case, the transformed values for JS^T_c are shown in Appendix Table A1 (and sample distribution by disability status), and ranging from -2.932 to 1.983 (for males), and -2.946 to 1.923 (for females). The main advantage of the POLS method compared to ordered probit models (OP) is, that when estimating panel data, the random/fixed effect error structure is much more easily implemented than with a similar model in the OP-framework (and also substantially reducing computational time), and the estimated coefficients are the marginal effects of the independent variables. In addition, POLS estimates (both coefficients and standard errors) are similar to OP estimates (except for a multiplicative factor), and are especially useful in the presence of ordinal variables among regressors (see Terza 1987; van Praag and Ferrer-i- Carbonell 2008). The drawback is that a harsher normality assumption is needed. The POLS method may be implemented by using a random or fixed effect specification. To choose between these two alternatives, we have run a Hausman test, and the results confirm the rejection of the random effect specification at any level of significance. Therefore, we estimated the following fixed-effect POLS model:

$$JS^T_{it} = \beta X_{it} + \alpha_i + e_{it} \quad [3]$$

where JS^T_{it} denotes individual i 's job satisfaction (transformed variable) at time t , X_{it} represents the time-variant regressor matrix, β is the vector of coefficients to be estimated, α_i is the unobserved time-invariant individual effect, and e_{it} is the idiosyncratic error. We also report in our tables the estimated values of σ_u (standard deviation of residuals within

groups), σ_e (standard deviation of residuals overall), and ρ (intraclass correlation, and tells us how strongly the observations within each unit resemble each other).

Apart from our key variables “performance appraisal” and “disability” (and its corresponding interaction terms), we include in Equation [3] the explanatory variables used in the literature on job satisfaction in general (e.g. Clark and Oswald, 1996; Clark, 1997; Georgellis and Lange, 2007), and performance appraisal in particular (e.g. Brown and Heywood, 2005; Addison and Belfield, 2008; Grund and Silwka, 2009; Cornelissen et al., 2011; Kampkötter, 2017; Heywood et al., 2017). We include as regressors: age (16-24; 25-34; 35-44; 45-54; 55-64), years of education, being married, being German, risk tolerance (values from 0 (*not at all willing to take risks*) to 10 (*very willing to take risks*)), net wages (in logarithms), tenure with actual employer (and its square), actual working hours (including overtime), public sector, temporal contract, firm size (1= 1-19; 2= 20-199; 3= 200-2000; 4= >2000 workers), job security (1= very concerned, 2= somewhat concerned, 3= not concerned at all), occupation (9 dummies), industry (1 digit NACE code, 9 dummies), region of residence (16 Länders), and year of interview (4 dummies). Appendix Table A2 contains the definition of the variables used in this study.

As explained in the previous section, for robustness purposes we have also run some estimations including variables on the level of recognition of individuals at work. Since we only have information on these variables for the year 2011, we have run an OLS model, and using the same explanatory variables included in Equation [3].

4 Results

Descriptive analysis

Table 1 shows the mean levels of job satisfaction and percentage of workers (broken down by disability and gender) without and with performance appraisal (monetary *versus* non-monetary effects). The remaining two last columns in Table 1 show the results

obtained after running a test of equality of means or proportions between workers without and with disabilities.

Overall and consistent with the previous literature on job satisfaction and disability (e.g. McAfee and McNaughton, 1997; Burke, 1999; Renaud, 2002; Uppal 2005; Schur et al., 2009; Pagan and Malo, 2009; and Pagan 2011, 2014), we find that workers with disabilities (both males and females) have lower levels of job satisfaction as compared to workers without disabilities. For males, the overall job satisfaction differential is 1.6 points, whereas for females it is 1.26 points (according to a test of equality of means, both differentials are statistically significant at conventional levels).

Looking at the samples by performance appraisal, we observe that the largest differential (and significant) in job satisfaction against workers with disabilities is found for males subject to performance appraisal with monetary effects (2.05 points). In contrast, for females the largest differential (again significant) is found for those without any type of performance appraisal (1.32 points). Once again, these differentials are significant at the 5% level.

We have also run a test of equality of means between the mean job satisfaction obtained in the category “No” and the other two categories “Yes, without or with monetary effects”. We only find significant differences between the categories “No” and “Yes, with monetary effects”, but for all samples (In Table 1, we have denoted the statistical significance of this test with the superscript b). Namely, all workers (with disabilities or not) who receive performance appraisals with monetary effects report higher levels of job satisfaction compared to those who are not subject to performance appraisal, except for male workers with disabilities, who report lower levels of satisfaction under performance appraisal with monetary effects. This is fully in line with our first hypothesis and consistent with the results obtained by previous empirical works

on performance appraisal (e.g. Pettijohn et al., 2001; Agyare et al., 2013; Kampkötter, 2017).

[Table 1]

Table 1 also includes data on job satisfaction and sample distribution but only for those workers who are subject to performance appraisal with monetary effects on gross wages, annual bonuses, future raises and possible promotions. We have to bear in mind that this question included in the SOEP allows multiple responses. Once again, all differentials in terms of job satisfaction by disability status are statistically significant at 5%, especially for the categories “annual bonuses” (2.3 and 1.33 points in favour of males and females without disabilities, respectively), “future raises” (2.68 in favour of males without disabilities), and “gross wages” (1.61 in favour of females without disabilities). Only 35.2% of males with disabilities report effects of appraisal on gross wages, and 56.9% on future raises. On the contrary, these percentages are 41.1 and 61.4% for males without disabilities, respectively (with both differentials being statistically significant as we compared them to those for males without disabilities). For females, all differences in percentages (last column) are statistically significant at conventional levels. We find larger differentials between females without and with disabilities for possible promotions (12.8 percentage points), and future raises (7.2 percentage points). In contrast, we observe a differential in favour of females with disabilities for the category “annual bonuses” (3.8 percentage points). Comparing the results obtained for males and females with disabilities, overall we detect higher levels of job satisfaction for females as compared to males (5.73 *versus* 5.40, with the gap being statistically significant at 5%), especially if they are subject to performance appraisal with monetary effects (6.16 *versus* 5.09, with the gap once gain significant). In all cases except for the category “gross wages” (wherein the differential is not significant), females with disabilities report higher job satisfaction

scores than males with disabilities. For example, the levels of job satisfaction for females receiving future raises and possible promotions are 6.10 and 6.31 points, whereas for males with disabilities the levels are only 4.63 and 5.27 points, respectively. These results are in line with Clark (1997), and confirmed by Pagan and Malo (2009) for the particular case of workers with disabilities: females with disabilities have such low expectations about what they can obtain from work that they have higher satisfaction in almost any type of job with respect to males with disabilities. This is in line with our second hypothesis about a potential job satisfaction premium received by females with disabilities as compared to males with disabilities when a performance appraisal with monetary effects is developed and implemented.

Econometric analysis

To start with, Appendix Table A3 shows the mean values and standard deviation of the explanatory variables used to estimate Equation [3] for workers without and with disabilities (males and females). Overall, it is worthwhile mentioning that workers with disabilities are older, less educated, with lower wages and very concerned about their job security, highly located in low-skilled occupations and service sector, working lower hours per week and less risk tolerance, and higher tenure and presence in the public sector as compared to workers without disabilities. Table 2 presents the results obtained from the estimation of our job satisfaction equation for both genders, and using the fixed-effect POLS model proposed by van Praag et al. (2003). This table also includes the mean and standard deviation (in parenthesis) of the main explanatory variables used in the estimation process and for each sample for informational purposes.

Firstly, we have used the test proposed by Verbeek and Nijman (1992) for fixed-effects models in order to test the existence of a problem of selectivity in our estimations. To do this, these authors suggest the inclusion in Equation [1] of three additional explanatory

variables which allows us to check as to whether the pattern of missing observations in the panel affects the underlying regression (Baltagi and Song, 2006): a) the number of waves in which the i^{th} individual is presented in the whole panel; b) a binary variable taking the value 1 if and only if the i^{th} individual is observed over the entire sample, and 0 otherwise, and; c) a binary variable indicating whether the individual was observed in the previous wave. The results obtained from this test show the rejection of potential selection bias in all our estimations.

Turning to the econometric results shown in Table 2, as we expected, the coefficient on the variable “disabled” is negative and significant at the 1% level for the male and female samples (and again statistically equal according to a test of equality of coefficients), providing support for the previous studies of Burke (1999), Renaud (2002), Uppal (2005), Pagan and Malo (2009) and Pagan (2011, 2014). We also find that only those workers receiving performance appraisal with monetary effects have a premium in terms of job satisfaction as compared to those who are not subject to performance appraisal (reference category). Once again, this finding is consistent with previous studies on performance appraisal. This result is found for males and females, with the magnitude of the corresponding coefficients being very similar and statistically equal after applying a test of equality of coefficients.

[Table 2]

Looking at the interaction terms between disability and performance appraisal, we find that males with disabilities subject to performance appraisal with monetary effects report dissatisfaction with their jobs compared to the reference category (i.e. those disabled with no performance appraisal). Namely, although having performance appraisal with monetary effects contributes to increasing the levels of satisfaction reported by all

workers (around 0.08 points), the total effect for males with disabilities is negative, -0.1849 points ($= 0.0771 - 0.262$), which is in line with our first hypothesis.

As noted earlier, this result may be partly due to the fact that males with disabilities may be suffering from unfair monetary outcomes (e.g. wages and/or promotions) as compared to other workers with similar characteristics and inputs, particularly due to the lack of more personalised performance systems that take into account the specific necessities and requirements they demand, as shown by the evidence provided by Schantz et al. (2018) and Witte (1998), but also by Stone and Colella (1996), Lengnick-Hall et al., (2008). Accordingly, the lack of fulfilment of males with disabilities' expectations about monetary rewards from an unfair performance system leads to a penalization in their job satisfaction scores. Unfortunately, the SOEP does not include any additional information on the existence of personalised or unfair performance systems within the workplace. Nevertheless, below we will provide some additional evidence from regressions on recognition variables –summarized in Table 4– from our database to support this interpretation of the results.

In contrast, the coefficient on the interaction term “Disabled * Yes, with monetary effects” for the female sample is positive and significant at the 5% level as compared to the reference category, with the total effect being positive and equal to 0.4312 points ($= 0.0822 + 0.349$). Therefore, this result for females with disabilities is in line with our second hypothesis, because performance appraisal does not decrease their job satisfaction and even it is positive. We also found a positive effect for females without disabilities (0.0822), but clearly lower than for those with disabilities (0.4312). As noted earlier, lower expectations about work for females with disabilities (Pagan, and Malo, 2009) may be behind this result. The idea of relative worker expectations introduced by Clark (1997), wherein females report lower expectations about their jobs than males, may suggest that

females with disabilities are less sensitive to -and less affected by- potential unfair performance systems than their male counterparts. Thus, the simple fact of receiving monetary rewards after a performance appraisal has a strong influence on increasing their levels of job satisfaction.

To sum up, we have summarised the results related to the two hypotheses in Table 3. In this table, we see that performance appraisal with monetary effects increases job satisfaction, but not for males with disabilities, for whom we find a negative impact (hypothesis 1). Table 3 also shows that females with disabilities have, *ceteris paribus*, higher levels of satisfaction than males with disabilities when they are subject to performance appraisal with monetary effects (hypothesis 2). Both effects are more intense for males and females with disabilities than for their counterparts without disabilities, lower in the case of males and higher for females -always comparing respect to those without disabilities.

[Table 3]

As for the remaining variables included in our model, their corresponding coefficients have the expected signs and are in line with the existing literature.

Complementary regressions on recognition

Using the responses to four questions concerning the level of recognition that workers feel at work (only for the year 2011), we have estimated OLS regressions on the level of recognition from superiors, for their efforts, personal advances, and pay. These estimations capture statistical associations and not causal effects, but they are good complements of previous analysis shedding some light about what may be behind the previous results.

In order to have richer results on incentives' schemes, we have followed the work of Heywood *et al.* (2017) which introduces the possibility to identify short-term monetary

effects (those on monthly gross wage and/or annual bonuses) *versus* long-term monetary effects (those on future earning and/or possible promotions), and have divided the total sample of workers subject to performance appraisal with monetary effects into three mutually exclusive groups: a) appraisals with only short-term consequences; b) appraisals with only long-term consequences, and; c) appraisals with both short- and long-term consequences. Following Kampkötter (2017), positive feedback from superiors may be perceived as recognition for work well-done and affects job satisfaction positively. Even negative feedback may contribute to detecting needs for training, and the need for more flexible schedules or reasonable workplace accommodations -particularly, for workers with disabilities.

Table 4 presents the results in a similar manner to the first panel of Table 2, offering the results for the disabled dummy, the set of dummies for the different performance appraisal schemes, and the interaction terms of being disabled and the performance appraisal schemes. Note that the coefficient on “disabled” captures the variation in recognition associated with being disabled and without performance appraisals. Being disabled for females is negatively associated with the recognition from superiors and according with the effort, independently of any type of any performance appraisal. In the rest of types of recognition, disabled females present also a negative association, although not statistically significant. These findings seem to be consistent with the proposition of lower expectations about work for females with disabilities as compared to their male counterparts (Clark, 1997; Pagan and Malo, 2009). For males, being disabled does not affect significantly to any type of recognition, although all estimated coefficients have a negative sign, as in the case of non-significant coefficients for females.

Considering the joint effect of disability and the different performance appraisal schemes, we find that, in general, there is a gendered pattern, as shown in the set of

interaction terms in Table 4. This pattern, with some few exceptions, consists of negative coefficients for males and positive effects for females⁵. For the exceptions, the positive coefficients for males are always lower than those for women. These results are coherent with the cross-gender heterogeneity in the performance appraisal effects for workers with disabilities shown in Table 2 and Table 3. At the same time, in general we do not have this gendered pattern for workers without disabilities⁶. Again, this is coherent with the absence of substantial or systematic differences across genders in the performance appraisal effects on job satisfaction for workers without disabilities shown in Table 2 and Table 3.

The negative effects on recognition of performance appraisal for males with disabilities, may suggest subjective unfair long-term rewards (in terms of future wages raises, possible promotions, etc.) as compared to their non-disabled peers, in the same line of problems of trust highlighted by Shantz et al. (2018). Why this “unfairness” effect is not dominant for women with disabilities is probably related to the well-known gender differences in fairness perception of own wages and wage growth in general (Pfeiffer and Stephan, 2018), and in job satisfaction in particular (Clark, 1997; Pagan and Malo, 2009). In fact, the empirical evidence, such as that from Pfeiffer and Stepahn (2018), points out that social norms and inherited gender roles are at least partly responsible for the propensity of women to perceive their wages as fair more often. Here, an explicit action providing women with better information about their relative wages, learning wage negotiation techniques and how to search for a better job, etc., would be reasonable

⁵ The total effect of performance appraisal schemes for people with disabilities -obtained summing the corresponding coefficients on performance appraisal dummies and interactions- show the same gendered pattern.

⁶ Note that the total effect of performance appraisal schemes on recognitions for people without disabilities corresponds to the set of dummies for performance appraisal in Table 4 not considering the interaction terms.

options for providing a more accurate perception of wages for women, either disabled or not.

[Table 4]

Robustness checks

First, we have re-estimated all job satisfaction equations, but now using the official disability measure available in the SOEP and obtained from the following question: “*Are you officially registered as having a reduced capacity for work or of being severely disabled? (YES/NO)*”. Namely, individuals responding “*YES*” to this question are considered as “*people with disabilities*”. In practice, the German legislation (“*Severely Disabled Persons Act (SDPA), 1974*”) which was amended in 1986) follows a definition of disability based on proposals of the World Health Organization which defines “*disabled people as persons whose physical functions, mental capabilities or psychological health are highly likely to deviate, for more than six months, from the condition which is typical for the respective age and whose participation in social life is therefore impaired* (Neuntes Buch des Sozialgesetzbuches, SGB IX (Book 9 of the Social Code))”. The individual’s degree of disability (ranging from 1 to 100 %, or 0 % in the event that a disability status does not apply) reflects limitations of a person’s life chances, and is given *independent of the fitness to work in the present or a new occupation* (Lechner and Vazquez-Alvarez, 2011). Furthermore, if the disabled person’s status improves, the degree of disability may be adjusted or totally revoked by the competent “*Versorgungsamt*”. Despite the limitations of this official registration-based disability measure pointed out by Burkhauser and Schroeder (2007) (particularly that it is not likely to be directly comparable to a self-reported work limitation question), its use could reduce the issues related to potential endogeneity, reverse causality, and simultaneity of using a work-limitation disability measure.

Looking at Table 5, we find that the coefficients on the variable “*officially disabled*” in both samples are not significant at the 5% level, and different from those shown in Table 2. The potential existence of official registration-based disabled workers who do not have any work limitation in the samples (as noted earlier, because the official disability assessment does not reflect working ability and is independent of the person’s occupational history) may explain this opposite finding. However, the remaining coefficients on our key variables are quite similar to those shown in Table 2, except for the coefficient on the interaction term “*officially disabled * Yes, with monetary effects*” for the female sample which is not significant at the 5% level as compared to the reference category. Similar to Burkhauser and Schroeder (2007), this latter result may be explained by the fact that fewer women participate in the workforce, and hence are less likely to apply for official disability registration. Since our work-limitation disability indicator is based in part on the registration of a disability (i.e. those with a degree of disability of at least 53%), fewer women are present in this severely limited group, and this fact would modify the result for the coefficient shown in Table 5.

[Table 5]

Second, we have re-estimated our job satisfaction equations using the disaggregation of performance appraisal systems by short- and long-term effects (Heywood *et al.*, 2017), and their corresponding interaction terms with the variable “disabled”. According to Table 6, we find that overall, males with appraisals that have long-term effects or both short- and long-term effects are more likely to report higher levels of satisfaction (0.0842 and 0.087 points, respectively) as compared to those males who are not subject to performance appraisal (reference category). Only the interaction term “Disabled * Yes, with short-term and long-term effects” is statistically significant at the 5% level, but negative (-0.459 points). As a result, the total effect for those males with disabilities

remains once again negative, -0.372 points ($= 0.087-0.459$), and even larger than that found in Table 2 and reported in Table 3 (i.e. -0.1849 points). Once again, this finding suggests a sense of unfairness and dissatisfaction in relation with the short and long-term outcomes of males with disabilities compared to those of their non-disabled counterparts.

For females, the job satisfaction premium is only found for those receiving both short- and long-term rewards (a significant and positive coefficient, 0.12 points) compared to the reference category. Looking at the interaction term, we only have a significant and positive coefficient on “Disabled * Yes, with long-term effects” (0.678 points), and with a total effect of 0.798 points ($= 0.120+0.678$) on job satisfaction. This outcome suggests that the use of monetary rewards based on future raises in wages and/or possible promotion (i.e. long-term rewards) becomes a key instrument to enhance females with disabilities’ job satisfaction scores.

[Table 6]

Finally, we would like to remark that we have estimated additional regressions as those shown in Table 2 but including additional interaction terms, first, between “risk tolerance” and “disability status”, and, second, between a “public/private sector” dummy and “performance appraisal”. The rationale for checking the importance of the risk variable was considering that we can presume that workers with disabilities are more risk averse than the rest of workers, and this might explain the results and not the performance related schemes. However, all the main results obtained remained. About the sector dummy, usually public sector workers have higher intrinsic motivation and are relatively more risk-averse, and, as a result, pecuniary incentives and variable pay may be counter-productive (Burguess and Ratto, 2003; Prendergast, 2008). Again, the main results remained. All these estimations are available upon request.

5 Conclusions

In this article, we have estimated the relationship between performance appraisal and job satisfaction by disability status and gender. In particular, we have focused on the effect of performance appraisal with monetary effects. Our results add to the very scarce empirical literature on incentives' schemes and disability (Witte et al., 1998; Shantz et al., 2018), providing novel results by gender. We have proposed two hypotheses: 1) performance appraisal with monetary effects decreases job satisfaction among male workers with disabilities because of “unfairness” feelings; and 2) performance appraisal with monetary effects does not decrease job satisfaction among females with disabilities because of lower expectations about their jobs.

Our findings are in line with both hypotheses. In general, performance appraisal with monetary effects increases job satisfaction, but the results differ by the disability status. For females with disabilities the increase in job satisfaction is much larger than for those without disabilities, while for males with disabilities there is even a total negative effect. At the same time, males and females without disabilities do not present significant differences in the positive impact of performance appraisal with monetary effects. Therefore, the strong differences of the effects of performance appraisal on job satisfaction by gender only exist among people with disabilities.

We have explored the association of disability and performance appraisal schemes with different types of recognition to have a glimpse what may be behind these differences. We find a coherent pattern respect to previous results. In general, there is a negative association of performance appraisal with monetary effects on recognition with pay for males with disabilities. We interpret this negative association as the channel for the above-cited negative effect on job satisfaction, which is coherent with the Equity Theory (Adams, 1963). We consider that these results suggest that the implementation of

performance appraisal schemes should properly take into account the disability status, especially for schemes with monetary effects. This is important for organizations, because this type of schemes is implemented to improve productivity. A known side effect of some performance-related pay schemes is work intensification and psychological stress (Lucifora, 2015), which may be detrimental for workers with disabilities and organizations must be aware of this problem. Drawing up guides for supervisors to understand how disabilities may affect the level and evolution of individual performance maybe useful to address these problems. Finally, the heterogeneity of workers in terms of their disability status must explicitly be part of union claims when bargaining or reviewing performance appraisal schemes.

Conversely, women have a positive association as the same type of interaction shows a positive effect on job satisfaction of being disabled and subject to performance appraisal with long-term monetary effects. The same analysis of the different dimensions of recognition shows a consistent positive effect of being disabled and subject to a performance appraisal with long-term monetary effects. This difference by gender may be understood as a different evaluation of expectations about jobs for women. As previous literature has shown that for women (Clark, 1997), older workers with disabilities (Pagan, 2011), and, specifically, women with disabilities (Pagan and Malo, 2009), these higher levels of satisfaction by gender (*ceteris paribus*) are in line with lower expectations about jobs, we consider that, in our context, probably we have the same type of effect via lower expectations about jobs than males and males with disabilities. Increasing information for women, especially for those with disabilities, about compensation in the firm would affect to their awareness about what is a 'fair' or 'unfair' performance appraisal. Providing reliable and public information about all employees may also be part of the claims of unions when an organization implements a performance appraisal with monetary effects.

To sum up, the effects of performance appraisal with monetary effects on job satisfaction for male workers with disabilities may be associated to a sort of “unfairness” perception, while for female workers they are closer to a “low expectation” effect or, conversely, a more frequent perception of their own wages and wage growth as fair. Possible actions suggested linked to previous literature are explicit, trustworthy and inclusive human resource management for workers with disabilities, especially to attend to differences related to disability in job performance when evaluation schemes are implemented by firms. This would be in benefit of men and women. At the same time, specific actions for women would be advisable -and also for women with disabilities- in relation to improving information about pay in different jobs, strategies for wage negotiation and a more informed job search. In any case, we need to go beyond some limitations of the empirical analysis of this research, based on observational data. A promising line for future research would be to have an experimental or cuasi-experimental evaluation of the implementation of a performance appraisal scheme with monetary effects, including workers without and with disabilities of both genders. This approach would allow to estimate the causal impact of a specific performance appraisal scheme on job satisfaction and analysing the causal channels for the impact. Of course, this type of approach would enjoy high internal validity but not necessarily external validity, and several studies on different performance appraisal schemes would be needed to generalize its results.

References

Adams, J. (1963). Toward an understanding of inequity. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 67(5), 422-436.

- Addison, J., & Belfield, C. (2008). The determinants of performance appraisal systems: a note (Do brown and Heywood's results for Australia hold up for Britain?). *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, 46, 521–531.
- Agyare, R., Yuhui, G., Mensah, L., Aidoo, Z., & Ansah, I. (2016). The impacts of performance appraisal on employees' job satisfaction and organizational commitment: a case of microfinance institutions in Ghana. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 11 (9), 281-297.
- Baldwin, M., & Johnson, W. (2006). A Critical Review of Studies of Discrimination against Workers with Disabilities. In *Handbook on the Economics of Discrimination*, edited by William M. Rodgers III, pp. 119-60. Northampton, MA: Edgar Elgar Publishing.
- Baltagi, B., & Song, S. (2006). Unbalanced panel data: A survey. *Statistical Papers*, 47(4), 493-523.
- Bonsang, E., & van Soest, A. (2012). Satisfaction with job and income among older individuals across European countries. *Social Indicators Research*, 105, 227-254.
- Brown, M., & Heywood, J. (2005). Performance appraisal systems: determinants and change. *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, 43(4), 659-679.
- Burgess, S., & Ratto, M. (2003). The role of incentives in the public sector: Issues and evidence. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy* 19(2): 285-300.
- Burke, R., (1999). Disability & women's work experiences: An explanatory study. *International Journal of Sociology and Social policy*, 19(2), 21-33.
- Burkhauser, R., & Daly, M. (1998). Disability and work: The experiences of American and German men. *Economic Review*, 2, 17-29.
- Burkhauser, R., Houtenville, A., & Rovba, L. (2006). Accounting for the declining fortunes of working-age people with disabilities. *Cornell Working Paper*, March.

- Burkhauser, R., & Schroeder, M. (2007). A method for comparing the economic outcomes of the working-age population with disabilities in Germany and the United States. *Journal of Applied Social Science Studies*, 127(2), 227-258.
- Clark, A. (1997). Job satisfaction and gender: Why are women so happy at work? *Labour Economics*, 4(4), 341-372.
- Clark, A., & Oswald, A. (1996). Satisfaction and comparison income. *Journal of Public Economics*, 61(3), 359-381.
- Cornelissen, T., Heywood, J., & Jirjahn, U. (2011). Performance pay, risk attitudes and job satisfaction. *Labour Economics*, 18, 229-239.
- Deepa, E., Palaniswamy, R., & Kuppusamy, S. (2014). Effect of performance appraisal system in organizational commitment, job satisfaction and productivity. *Journal of Contemporary Management Research*, 8 (1), 72-82.
- Ferrer-i-Carbonell, A., & Frijters, P. (2004). How important is methodology for the estimates of the determinants of happiness? *The Economic Journal*, 114(497), 641-659.
- Franco, L.M., Bennett, S., & Kanfer, R. (2002). Health sector reform and public sector health worker motivation: A conceptual framework, *Social Science and Medicine*, 54(8): 1255-1266.
- Georgellis, Y., & Lange, T. (2007). Participation in continuous, on-the-job training and the impact on job satisfaction: Longitudinal evidence from the German labour market. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 18(6), 969-985.
- Gielen, A. C., Kerkhofs, M., & van Ours, J. C. (2010). How performance related pay affects productivity and employment. *Journal of Population Economics* 23(1), 291-301.

- Grimby, G., Finnstram, J., & Jette, A. (1988). On application of the WHO handicap classification in rehabilitation. *Scandinavian Journal of Rehabilitation Medicine*, 20, 93-98.
- Grund, C., & Sliwka, D. (2009). The anatomy of performance appraisals in Germany. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 20(10), 2049-2065.
- Grund, C., & Przemeczek, J. (2012). Subjective performance appraisal and inequality aversion. *Applied Economics*, 44, 2149-2155.
- Herzberg F. (1968). One more time: how do you motivate employees? *Harvard Business Review*, 46(1), 53-62.
- Heywood, J., Jirjahn, U., & Struewing, C. (2017). Locus of control and performance appraisal. *Journal of Economics Behavior & Organization*, 142, 205-225.
- Heywood, J., & Wei, X. (2006). Performance Pay and Job Satisfaction. *Journal of Industrial Relations*, 48(4), 523-540.
- Huseman, R., Hatfield, J., & Miles, E. (1987). A new perspective on equity theory. *Academy of Management Review*, 12(2), 222-234.
- Jackson, S., & Schuler, R. (2003). *Managing Human Resources through Strategic Partnership*. Canada: Thompson.
- Jenkins, S., & Riggs, J. (2004). Disability and disadvantage: Selection, onset, and duration effects. *Journal of Social Policy*, 33(3), 479-501.
- Jirjahn, U., & Poutsma, E. (2013). The use of performance appraisal systems: evidence from Dutch establishment data. *Industrial Relations*, 52, 801-821.
- Judge, T., Bono, J., Thoresen, C., & Patton, G. (2001). The job satisfaction-job performance relationship: A qualitative and quantitative review. *Psychological Bulletin*, 127, 376-407.

- Kampkötter, P. (2017). Performance appraisals and job satisfaction. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 28(5), 750-774.
- Keeping, L., & Levy, P. (2000). Performance appraisal reactions: measurement, modeling and method bias. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 85, 708-23.
- Kennedy, P. (1995). Performance Pay, Productivity and Morale. *Economic Record*, 71(3), 251-258.
- King, G., Murray, C., Salomon, J., & Tandon, A. (2004). Enhancing the validity and cross-cultural comparability of measurement in survey research. *American Political Science Review*, 98(1), 567-583.
- Knott, R., Lorgelly, P., Black, N., & Hollingsworth, B. (2017). Differential item functioning in quality of life measurement: An analysis using anchoring vignettes. *Social Science & Medicine*, 190, 247-255.
- Kristensen, N., & Johansson, E. (2008). New evidence on cross-country differences in job satisfaction using anchoring vignettes. *Labour Economics*, 15, 96-117.
- Lazear, E. (2000). Performance pay and productivity." *American Economic Review* 90(5): 1346–1361.
- Lechner, M., & Vazquez-Alvarez, R. (2011). The effect of disability on labour market outcomes in Germany. *Applied Economics*, 43(4), 389-412.
- Lengnick-Hall, M., Gaunt, P., & Kulkarni, M. (2008). Overlooked and underutilized: People with disabilities are an untapped human resource. *Human Resource Management*, 47(2), 255-273.
- Levy, P., & Williams, J. (2004). The social context of performance appraisal: a review and framework for the future. *Journal of Management*, 30, 881-906.

- Liao, H. (2007). Do it right this time: the role of employee service recovery performance in customer perceived justice and customer loyalty after service failures. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 92, 475-89.
- Lucifora, C. (2015). Performance-related pay and labor productivity. *IZA World of Labor* 2015:152.
- Lucifora, C., & Origo F. (2015). Performance-related pay and firm productivity: Evidence from a reform in the structure of collective bargaining. *Industrial and Labor Relations Review* 68(3): 606–632.
- Maddala, G. (1983). *Limited dependent and qualitative variables in econometrics*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Malo, M., & Pagan, R. (2012). Wage differentials and disability across Europe: Discrimination and/or lower productivity? *International Labour Review*, 151 (1/2), 43-60.
- McAfee, J., & McNaughton, D. (1997). Transitional outcomes: Job satisfaction of workers with disabilities part one: General job satisfaction. *Journal of Vocational Rehabilitation*, 8(2), 135-142.
- McNabb, R., & Whitfield, K. (2007). The impact of varying types of performance-related pay and employee participation on earnings. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 18(6): 1004-1025.
- Milkovich, G., & Wigdor, A. (1991). *Pay for Performance: Evaluating Performance Appraisal and Merit Pay*. Washington DC: National Academy Press.
- Ng, Y. (1997). A case of happiness, cardinalism, and interpersonal comparability. *Economic Journal*, 107(445), 1848-1858.
- Pagan, R. (2010). Onset of disability and life satisfaction: Evidence from the German socio-economic panel. *European Journal of Health Economics*, 11(5), 471-485.

- Pagan, R. (2011). Ageing and disability: job satisfaction differentials across Europe. *Social Science and Medicine*, 72(2), 206-215.
- Pagan, R. (2014). What makes workers with disabilities happy? The importance of non-pecuniary characteristics. *Health Economics*, 23(2), 241-247.
- Pagan, R., & Malo, M. (2009). Job satisfaction and disability: Lower expectations about jobs or a matter of health? *Spanish Economic Review*, 11(1), 51-74.
- Pettijohn, C., Pettijohn, L., & d'Amico, M. (2001). Characteristics of performance appraisals and their impact on sales force satisfaction. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 12, 127-146.
- Pfeifer, C., & Stephan, G. (2018). Why women don't ask: Gender differences in fairness perceptions of own wages and subsequent wage growth. SOEP papers # 963, DIW-SOEP.
- Prendergast, C. (1999). The provision of incentives in firms. *Journal of Economic Literature* 37: 7-63.
- Prendergast, C. (2008). Intrinsic motivation and incentives. *American Economic Review* 98:2.
- Renaud, S. (2002). Rethinking the union membership/job satisfaction relationship: Some empirical evidence in Canada. *International Journal of Manpower*, 23(2), 137-150.
- Rowland, C., & Hall, R.D. (2012). Organizational justice and performance: is appraisal fair? *EuroMed Journal of Business*, 7(3), 280-293.
- Rupp, D., Bashshur, M., & Liao, H. (2007). Justice Climate Past, Present, and Future: Models of Structure and Emergence. In *Research in Multi-Level Issues*, Vol. 6, edited by Fred Dansereau, and Francis Yammarino, pp. 357-96. Oxford: Elsevier.
- Schwartz, N. (1995). What respondents learn from questionnaires: the survey interview and the logic of conversation. *International Statistical Review*, 63(2), 153-177.

- Shantz, A., Wang, J., & Malik, A. (2018). Disability status, individual variable pay, and pay satisfaction: Does relational and institutional trust make a difference? *Human Resources Management*, 57, 365-380.
- Schur, L., Kruse, D., Blasi, J., & Blanck, P. (2009). Is disability disabling in all workplaces? Workplaces disparities and corporate culture. *Industrial Relations*, 48(3), 381-410.
- Stapleton, D., & Burkhauser, R. (2003). A user's guide to current statistics on the employment of people with disabilities. In D. Stapleton and R. Burkhauser (Eds.), *The decline in employment of people with disabilities, a policy puzzle*. Michigan: W.E. Upjohn Institute for Employment Research.
- Stone, D., & Colella, A. (1996). A model of factors affecting the treatment of disabled individuals in organizations. *Academy of Management Review*, 21(2), 352-401.
- Terza, J. (1987). Estimating linear models with ordinal qualitative regressors. *Journal of Econometrics*, 34, 275-291.
- Thurston, P., & McNall, L. (2010). Justice perceptions of performance practices. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 25(3), 201-228.
- Uppal, S. (2005). Disability, workplace characteristics and job satisfaction. *International Journal of Manpower*, 26(4), 336-349.
- Van Praag, B. (1991). Ordinal and cardinal utility: an integration of the two dimensions of the welfare concept. *Journal of Econometrics*, 50 (1-2), 69-89.
- Van Praag, B., & Ferrer-i-Carbonell, A. (2006). An Almost Integration-free Approach to Ordered Response Models. Tinbergen Institute Discussion Paper n° 2006-047/3.
- Van Praag, B., & Ferrer-i-Carbonell, A. (2008). *Quantified happiness: A satisfaction calculus approach*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

- Van Praag, B., Frijters, P., & Ferrer-i-Carbonell, A. (2003). The anatomy of subjective well-being. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 51(1), 29-49.
- Verbeek, M., & Nijman, T. (1992). Non-response in panel data: The impact on estimates of a life cycle consumption function. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 7(3), 243-257.
- Wagner, G., Frick, J., & Schupp, J. (2007). The German socio-economic panel study (SOEP): scope, evolution and enhancements. *Journal of Applied Social Science Studies*, 127(1), 139-169.
- Whitman, D., Van Rooy, D., & Viswesvaran, C. (2010). Satisfaction, citizenship behaviors, and performance in work units: A meta-analysis of collective construct relations. *Personnel Psychology*, 63(1), 41-81.
- Witte, R. H., Philips, L., & Kakela, M. (1998). Job satisfaction of college graduates with learning disabilities. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 31(3), 259–265

Table 1 Mean job satisfaction scores (JS) and percentage of workers with and without performance appraisal (%) by disability status and gender in Germany.

MALES						
	WORKERS WITHOUT DISABILITIES		WORKERS WITH DISABILITIES		<i>Difference in JS</i>	<i>Difference in %</i>
	JS	%	JS	%		
Performance appraisal:						
No	6.96	62.2	5.51	68.9	1.45 ^a	-6.7 ^a
Yes, without monetary effects	6.87	9.8	5.31	9.7	1.56 ^a	0.1
Yes, with monetary effects	7.14 ^b	28.0	5.09 ^b	21.4	2.05 ^a	6.6 ^a
<i>Total =</i>	7.00	100	5.40	100	1.60 ^a	
<i>Only for those with monetary effects:</i>						
Influence on: (multiple responses)						
Gross wages	7.13	41.1	5.76	35.2	1.37 ^a	5.9 ^a
Annual bonuses	7.16	59.2	4.86	59.0	2.30 ^a	0.2
Future raises	7.31	61.4	4.63	56.9	2.68 ^a	4.5 ^a
Possible promotion	7.25	67.2	5.27	65.1	1.98 ^a	2.1
FEMALES						
	WORKERS WITHOUT DISABILITIES		WORKERS WITH DISABILITIES		<i>Difference in JS</i>	<i>Difference in %</i>
	JS	%	JS	%		
Performance appraisal:						
No	6.96	70.1	5.64	73.9	1.32 ^a	-3.8 ^a
Yes, without monetary effects	6.99	12.1	5.79	12.6	1.20 ^a	-0.5
Yes, with monetary effects	7.07 ^b	17.8	6.16 ^b	13.5	0.91 ^a	4.3 ^a
<i>Total =</i>	6.99	100	5.73	100	1.26 ^a	
<i>Only for those with monetary effects:</i>						
Influence on: (multiple responses)						
Gross wages	7.09	32.8	5.48	28.7	1.61 ^a	4.1 ^a
Annual bonuses	6.9	58.4	5.65	62.2	1.33 ^a	-3.8 ^a
Future raises	7.20	55.7	6.10	48.5	1.10 ^a	7.2 ^a
Possible promotion	7.17	65.5	6.31	52.7	0.86 ^a	12.8 ^a

Note: Sample consists of workers aged 16-64. We exclude self-employed, freelance professionals, apprentices, trainees, and those with a monthly net salary less than 450 euros. Weighted data. ^a Difference between people without and with disabilities is significant at $P < 0.05$. ^b Difference between “No” and “Yes, without/with monetary effects” is significant at $P < 0.05$.

Source: SOEP for the years 2004, 2008, 2011, and 2016. Number of observations: workers without disabilities = 18,166 males and 17,254 females, and workers with disabilities = 813 males and 752 females.

Table 2 Job satisfaction regressions (POLS individual fixed effects) for males and females in Germany.

	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Males</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Females</i>
Disabled	0.037	-0.373*** (0.0876)	0.038	-0.365*** (0.101)
Performance appraisal:				
No (<i>reference</i>)	0.611	-	0.669	-
Yes, without monetary effects	0.093	0.0103 (0.0368)	0.133	0.0167 (0.0363)
Yes, with monetary effects	0.296	0.0771*** (0.0278)	0.198	0.0822*** (0.0340)
Interaction terms:				
Disabled * Yes, without monetary effects	0.004	0.173 (0.151)	0.006	0.087 (0.230)
Disabled * Yes, with monetary effects	0.011	-0.262** (0.124)	0.007	0.349** (0.176)
Risk tolerance	5.154 (2.164)	0.0169*** (0.00650)	4.422 (2.178)	0.0228*** (0.0069)
Ln (wages)	7.603 (0.477)	0.192*** (0.063)	7.124 (0.512)	0.100* (0.056)
Actual working hours	46.423 (10.557)	-0.0039*** (0.0014)	36.621 (11.792)	-0.0061*** (0.0018)
Tenure	12.352 (10.485)	-0.0431*** (0.0045)	10.862 (9.751)	-0.0414*** (0.0053)
Tenure ²	262.501 (374.05)	0.00056*** (0.00012)	213.049 (328.68)	0.00051*** (0.00015)
Industry dummies		Yes		Yes
Occupation dummies		Yes		Yes
Region dummies		Yes		Yes
Year dummies		Yes		Yes
<i>Constant</i>	-	-1.2901* (0.668)	-	-0.0047 (0.927)
σ_u		0.949		0.956
σ_e		0.709		0.740
ρ		0.642		0.626
Number of observations		15,679		14,036
Number of individuals		9,140		8,533

Note: All regressions also include: age, married, years of education, being German, public sector, temporal contract, firm size and job security. The standard errors are robust and allow for clustering at an individual level. *, **, *** imply significance at the 10, 5, and 1% level, respectively. Workers aged 16-64 years. **Source:** SOEP for the years 2004, 2008, 2011 and 2016.

Table 3 Summary of results: Total effects of performance appraisal with monetary effects by disability status and gender.

	<i>Males</i>	<i>Females</i>
Without disabilities	0.0711***	0.0822***
With disabilities	-0.1849** (= -0.0771-0.262)	0.4312** (= 0.0822+0.349)

*, **, *** imply significant at the 10, 5, and 1% level, respectively.

Table 4 Recognition from superiors, with efforts, advance and pay (OLS regressions) for males and females in Germany (2011).

	<i>Recognition from superiors</i>		<i>Recognition with efforts</i>		<i>Recognition with advances</i>		<i>Recognition with pay</i>	
	<i>Males</i>	<i>Females</i>	<i>Males</i>	<i>Females</i>	<i>Males</i>	<i>Females</i>	<i>Males</i>	<i>Females</i>
Disabled	-0.159 (0.144)	-0.411*** (0.150)	-0.204 (0.152)	-0.333** (0.137)	-0.0920 (0.135)	-0.153 (0.137)	-0.0629 (0.170)	-0.152 (0.159)
Performance appraisal:								
Yes, without monetary effects	-0.0494 (0.0807)	-0.0112 (0.0763)	-0.0324 (0.0817)	0.00568 (0.0749)	-0.148* (0.0827)	-0.0234 (0.0699)	-0.131 (0.0900)	0.0755 (0.0788)
Yes, with short-term effects	0.0738 (0.0773)	-0.0158 (0.0909)	0.0232 (0.0771)	-0.0402 (0.0871)	-0.0588 (0.0766)	-0.0838 (0.0897)	0.0344 (0.0832)	-0.0800 (0.0925)
Yes, with long-term effects	0.179** (0.0783)	0.181** (0.0864)	0.172** (0.0800)	0.0981 (0.0886)	0.191** (0.0840)	-0.00157 (0.0883)	0.0300 (0.0916)	0.0582 (0.0967)
Yes, with short-term & long-term effects	0.0172 (0.0653)	0.308*** (0.0783)	0.0908 (0.0652)	0.174** (0.0801)	-0.0386 (0.0645)	0.153** (0.0767)	0.0280 (0.0722)	0.198** (0.0832)
Interaction terms:								
Disabled * Yes, without monetary effects	-0.236 (0.326)	0.401 (0.350)	-0.265 (0.327)	0.133 (0.360)	-0.435 (0.334)	-0.411 (0.365)	-0.350 (0.348)	0.0282 (0.380)
Disabled * Yes, with short-term effects	-0.0910 (0.290)	0.612 (0.431)	-0.219 (0.302)	0.561 (0.422)	-0.325 (0.326)	0.0990 (0.344)	0.324 (0.321)	0.578 (0.437)
Disabled * Yes, with long-term effects	0.209 (0.355)	0.732** (0.323)	0.213 (0.312)	0.816*** (0.283)	-0.649 (0.416)	1.092*** (0.257)	-0.925*** (0.299)	0.633** (0.259)
Disabled * Yes, with short-term & long-term effects	-0.193 (0.391)	-0.0380 (0.379)	-0.280 (0.372)	-0.624 (0.440)	0.175 (0.343)	-0.450 (0.375)	-0.482 (0.380)	-0.545 (0.440)
<i>Constant</i>	3.283*** (0.497)	3.569*** (0.535)	3.053*** (0.508)	3.302*** (0.524)	2.170*** (0.498)	3.454*** (0.503)	-2.830*** (0.611)	-0.375 (0.570)
Number of observations	2,972	2,703	2,965	2,685	2,950	2,632	2,978	2,694

Note: All regressions include the remaining explanatory variables shown in Table 2. The standard errors are robust. *, **, *** imply significance at the 10, 5, and 1% level, respectively. Workers aged 16-64 years. Source: SOEP for the year 2011.

Table 5 Job satisfaction regressions (POLS individual fixed effects) for males and females in Germany by using the worker's official disability status.

	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Males</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Females</i>
Officially disabled	0.064	0.0029 (0.079)	0.054	-0.0844 (0.077)
Performance appraisal:				
No (<i>reference</i>)	0.610	-	0.670	-
Yes, without monetary effects	0.094	0.0309 (0.0379)	0.132	0.00183 (0.0379)
Yes, with monetary effects	0.296	0.0789*** (0.0285)	0.198	0.102*** (0.0350)
Interaction terms:				
Officially disabled * Yes, without monetary effects	0.008	-0.121 (0.115)	0.008	0.232 (0.157)
Officially disabled * Yes, with monetary effects	0.018	-0.198** (0.0982)	0.011	-0.199 (0.134)
<i>Constant</i>	-	-1.380** (0.666)	-	-0.166 (0.919)
σ_u		0.953		0.962
σ_e		0.712		0.740
ρ		0.642		0.628
Number of observations		15,649		14,002
Number of individuals		9,128		8,522

Note: All regressions include the remaining explanatory variables shown in Table 2. The standard errors are robust and allow for clustering at an individual level. *, **, *** imply significance at the 10, 5, and 1% level, respectively. Workers aged 16-64 years.
Source: SOEP for the years 2004, 2008, 2011 and 2016.

Table 6 Job satisfaction regressions (POLS individual fixed effects) taking into account the type of monetary effects (short, long and short/long term) for males and females in Germany.

	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Males</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Females</i>
Disabled	0.037	-0.372*** (0.0878)	0.038	-0.368*** (0.102)
Performance appraisal:				
No (<i>reference</i>)	0.611	-	0.669	-
Yes, without monetary effects	0.093	0.0109 (0.0370)	0.133	0.0167 (0.0364)
Yes, with short-term effects	0.086	0.0591 (0.0371)	0.062	0.0700 (0.0490)
Yes, with long-term effects	0.073	0.0842** (0.0403)	0.062	0.0654 (0.0497)
Yes, with short-term & long-term effects	0.137	0.0870** (0.0363)	0.074	0.120** (0.0483)
Interaction terms:				
Disabled * Yes, without monetary effects	0.004	0.183 (0.152)	0.006	0.0834 (0.229)
Disabled * Yes, with short-term effects	0.004	-0.162 (0.216)	0.002	0.0855 (0.238)
Disabled * Yes, with long-term effects	0.003	-0.0814 (0.202)	0.002	0.678** (0.297)
Disabled * Yes, with short-term & long-term effects	0.004	-0.459** (0.187)	0.003	0.339 (0.245)
<i>Constant</i>	-	-1.301* (0.669)	-	-0.00794 (0.925)
σ_u		0.949		0.956
σ_e		0.709		0.739
ρ		0.642		0.626
Number of observations		15,679		14,036
Number of individuals		9,140		8,533

Note: All regressions include the remaining explanatory variables shown in Table 2. . The standard errors are robust and allow for clustering at an individual level. *, **, *** imply significance at the 10, 5, and 1% level, respectively. Workers aged 16-64 years.
Source: SOEP for the years 2004, 2008, 2011 and 2016.

Appendix

Table A1 Transformed values of the job satisfaction variable (applying Terza, 1987) used in Table 2 (POLS individual fixed effects) by gender, and sample distribution for non-disabled (ND) and disabled (N) workers.

Original job satisfaction variable (JS)	<i>Males</i>			<i>Females</i>		
	Transformed job satisfaction variable (JS^T_i)	ND (%)	D (%)	Transformed job satisfaction variable (JS^T_i)	ND (%)	D (%)
0	-2.932	0.33	3.24	-2.946	0.30	3.32
1	-2.435	0.55	3.24	-2.439	0.57	3.32
2	-2.066	1.49	10.39	-2.071	1.56	6.46
3	-1.705	2.92	8.69	-1.704	3.09	8.86
4	-1.415	3.58	6.64	-1.399	3.88	6.64
5	-1.060	9.59	15.16	-1.021	10.66	16.24
6	-0.678	10.88	11.07	-0.636	10.65	9.78
7	-0.240	20.57	14.65	-0.218	19.94	12.18
8	0.396	28.96	16.01	0.392	27.63	18.45
9	1.132	14.97	7.50	1.092	14.73	9.23
10	1.983	6.14	3.41	1.923	6.98	5.54
N° of observations	15,679	15,092	587	14,036	13,494	542

Table A2 Definition of variables.

Variable	Description
Job satisfaction	Individual's job satisfaction. Responses from 0 (completely dissatisfied) to 10 (completely satisfied)
Disabled (d)	=1 if the individual is disabled
Performance appraisal (d):	
No	=1 if the individual's performance is not assessed
Yes, without monetary effects	=1 if the individual's performance is assessed but without monetary effects
Yes, with monetary effects	=1 if the individual's performance is assessed and has monetary effects
Risk tolerance	Question: Are you generally a person who is fully prepared to take risks or do you try to avoid taking risks? Responses from 0 (risk averse) to 10 (fully prepared to take risks)
Ln (wages)	Net wage last month (in logarithms)
Tenure	Firm tenure in years
Actual working hours	Total working hours per week (including overtime)
Age groups (d):	
16-24	Individuals aged 16-24
25-34	Individuals aged 25-34
35-44	Individuals aged 35-44
45-54	Individuals aged 45-54
55-64	Individuals aged 55-64
Married (d)	=1 if the individual is married
Years of education	Years of education
German (d)	=1 if nationality is German
Public sector (d)	=1 if the individual works in the public sector
Temporal (d)	=1 if the individual has a temporal contract
Firm size (d):	
1-19 workers	=1 if firm size is smaller than 20 workers
20-199 workers	=1 if firm size is between 20 and 199 workers
200-2000 workers	=1 if firm size is between 200 and 2000 workers
>2000 workers	=1 if firm size is greater than 2000 workers
Job security (d):	
Very concerned	=1 if the individual is very concerned about his/her job security
Somewhat concerned	=1 if the individual is somewhat concerned about his/her job security
No concerned	=1 if the individual is not concerned at all about his/her job security
Occupation (d):	
Untrained BC	=1 if the individual is an untrained blue-collar worker
Semi-trained BC	=1 if the individual is a semi-trained blue-collar worker
Trained BC	=1 if the individual is a trained blue-collar worker
Foreman	=1 if the individual is a foreman/team leader worker
Simple tasks WC	=1 if the individual is a white collar worker with simple tasks
Qualified professional	=1 if the individual is a qualified professional worker
High qualified	=1 if the individual is a high qualified and managerial worker
Low/Middle civil service	=1 if the individual has a low-middle civil service
High civil service	=1 if the individual has a high-executive civil service
Industry (d):	
Agriculture	=1 if the firm is operating in the agricultural sector
Energy	=1 if the firm is operating in the energy sector

Mining	=1 if the firm is operating in the mining sector
Manufacturing	=1 if the firm is operating in the manufacturing sector
Construction	=1 if the firm is operating in the construction sector
Trade	=1 if the firm is operating in the trade sector
Transport	=1 if the firm is operating in the transport sector
Bank/insurance	=1 if the firm is operating in the bank/insurance sector
Services	=1 if the firm is operating in the service sector
Region of residence (d)	State of residence (16 Länders: Schleswig-Holstein, Hamburg, Lower Saxony, Bremen, North-Rhine-Westfalia, Hessen, Rheinland-Pfalz, Baden-Wuerttemberg, Bavaria, Saarland, Berlin, Brandenburg, Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, Saxony, Saxony-Anhalt, and Thuringia)
Year of interview (d)	Year in which the interview took place (2004, 2008, 2011 and 2016)
Recognition from superiors	Question: I receive the recognition I deserve from my superiors. Responses from 1 (No recognition, burdening very heavily) to 5 (Yes recognition)
Recognition with efforts	Question: When I consider all my accomplishments and efforts, the recognition I have received seems fitting. Responses from 1 (No recognition, burdening very heavily) to 5 (Yes recognition)
Recognition with advances	Question: When I consider all my accomplishments and efforts, my chances of personal advancement seem fitting. Responses from 1 (No recognition, burdening very heavily) to 5 (Yes recognition)
Recognition with pay	Question: When I consider all my accomplishments and efforts, my pay seems appropriate. Responses from 1 (No recognition, burdening very heavily) to 5 (Yes recognition)
Performance appraisal according to Heywood et al. (2017) (d):	
Yes, with short-term effects	=1 if the individual's performance is assessed and has monetary effects on monthly gross wage and/or annual bonuses
Yes, with long-term effects	=1 if the individual's performance is assessed and has monetary effects on future earning and/or possible promotions
Yes, with short/long term effects	=1 if the individual's performance is assessed and has monetary effects in the short and long term
Officially disabled (d)	=1 if the individual has been officially registered as having a reduced capacity for work or of being severely disabled

Note: (d) indicates dummy variables.

Table A3 Mean values and standard deviation (between parentheses) of explanatory variables used in Table 2 by disability status and gender.

Variables	Non-disabled		Disabled	
	<i>Males</i>	<i>Females</i>	<i>Males</i>	<i>Females</i>
Performance appraisal:				
No	0.610	0.606	0.670	0.655
Yes, without monetary effects	0.093	0.132	0.112	0.151
Yes, with monetary effects	0.297	0.198	0.281	0.194
Risk tolerance	5.177	4.440	4.550	3.993
	(2.155)	(2.168)	(2.311)	(2.369)
Ln (wages)	7.606	7.122	7.517	7.103
	(0.476)	(0.511)	(0.487)	(0.540)
Tenure	12.242	10.807	15.177	12.227
	(10.430)	(9.716)	(11.478)	(10.487)
Actual working hours	46.494	36.625	44.596	36.509
	(10.553)	(11.808)	(10.498)	(11.394)
Age groups:				
16-24	0.035	0.039	0.017	0.030
25-34	0.183	0.180	0.102	0.087
35-44	0.304	0.292	0.218	0.245
45-54	0.310	0.328	0.339	0.389
55-64	0.169	0.161	0.324	0.249
Married (d)	0.672	0.588	0.692	0.561
Years of education	12.784	12.983	12.494	12.538
	(2.811)	(2.688)	(2.789)	(2.665)
German (d)	0.907	0.929	0.968	0.919
Public sector (d)	0.225	0.357	0.266	0.413
Temporal (d)	0.083	0.106	0.053	0.103
Firm size:				
1-19 workers	0.170	0.230	0.177	0.155
20-199 workers	0.293	0.299	0.256	0.360
200-2000 workers	0.244	0.226	0.252	0.247
>2000 workers	0.293	0.246	0.315	0.238
Job security:				
Very concerned	0.122	0.115	0.204	0.203
Somewhat concerned	0.378	0.352	0.356	0.330
No concerned	0.500	0.533	0.440	0.467
Occupation:				
Untrained BC	0.021	0.031	0.026	0.057
Semi-trained BC	0.107	0.076	0.126	0.103
Trained BC	0.206	0.042	0.210	0.031
Foreman	0.058	0.006	0.056	0.013
Simple tasks WC	0.071	0.190	0.063	0.190
Qualified professional	0.181	0.434	0.199	0.382
High qualified	0.273	0.148	0.228	0.144
Low/Middle civil service	0.023	0.016	0.029	0.020
High civil service	0.060	0.058	0.063	0.059
Industry:				
Agriculture	0.016	0.006	0.010	0.007
Energy	0.017	0.007	0.020	0.011
Mining	0.004	0.001	0.003	0.000
Manufacturing	0.236	0.108	0.252	0.111
Construction	0.204	0.050	0.158	0.033
Trade	0.103	0.161	0.094	0.144
Transport	0.078	0.036	0.078	0.048
Bank/insurance	0.042	0.048	0.041	0.030
Services	0.300	0.582	0.342	0.616

Region of residence:				
Schleswig-Holstein	0.027	0.028	0.019	0.030
Hamburg	0.016	0.016	0.012	0.022
Lower Saxony	0.091	0.090	0.089	0.059
Bremen	0.007	0.008	0.003	0.002
North-Rhine-Westfalia	0.205	0.193	0.187	0.205
Hessen	0.071	0.073	0.082	0.068
Rheinland-Pfalz	0.049	0.047	0.048	0.037
Baden-Wuerttemberg	0.138	0.116	0.129	0.144
Bavaria	0.154	0.150	0.184	0.153
Saarland	0.010	0.011	0.020	0.009
Berlin	0.030	0.039	0.058	0.050
Brandenburg	0.034	0.042	0.031	0.033
Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	0.020	0.025	0.010	0.017
Saxony	0.070	0.076	0.044	0.081
Saxony-Anhalt	0.038	0.043	0.046	0.042
Thuringia	0.040	0.043	0.037	0.048
Year of interview:				
2004	0.268	0.246	0.281	0.240
2008	0.237	0.223	0.220	0.197
2011	0.190	0.192	0.242	0.225
2016	0.305	0.339	0.257	0.338
Number of observations	15,092	13,494	587	542